

Towards Robot Avatars in Industrial Applications

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Abstract—In the last years power computing and communication technologies have improved greatly, while at the same time immersive and wearable user interfaces became available at a consumer level. The widespread of these technologies fostered research in the field of telexistence and robot avatars, making it mature enough to be deployed out of the lab.

There is a general consensus that enabling the remotization of physical activities would have a large impact on both safety and efficiency of industrial processes. In this paper we report our work towards the development of robot avatars for industrial applications and the preliminary results of their deployment in real use cases.

Index Terms—robot avatar, metaverse, telexistence, technology transfer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Historically, robotic teleoperated systems were conceived to explore and operate in places with extreme conditions such as space [1], deep oceans water [2] or nuclear plants [3]. Among the challenges of these technology, it is worth mentioning communication delays, stability, lack of proper feedback, and not secondarily high development costs.

In the last 10 years, thanks to the exponential growth of computing capability of electronics devices, the market accelerated the development of novel wearable interfaces, e.g. VR head set, haptic devices and motion tracking suits, with a direct effect on the costs, making these technologies accessible at a consumer level. Such novel human interfaces enabled non expert users to control the robots in an intuitive fashion [4] and, consequently, lead to a more extensive development of the robot avatar technology in different fields, e.g. disaster scenarios [5], hospitals [6] and entertainment [7]. These research activities demonstrated that telexistence is a technology mature enough to have an impact also out of the lab in real applications, such as operations in dangerous, remote or poor working conditions within factories, in everyday life, such as garbage handling and scavenging, civil engineering, agriculture, forestry, elderly care and many others [8].

This work was developed within the JOiiNT LAB¹, which is a joint laboratory established between IIT² and Consorzio Intellimech³, dedicated to applied research and technological

Fig. 1. Examples of different applicative scenarios for the robot avatar technology, provided by the companies that are involved in the JOiiNT LAB.

transfer. One of its main research areas aims at evaluating the potential impact of robot avatars technology in real industrial use cases defined with the companies involved in the lab.

Interestingly, depending on the application, the same technology may answer to various needs. Fig. 1 provides a perspective of the different requirements and use cases we are exploring jointly with Cosberg, Fassi, Siad and Valtellina.

In this paper we report our work for the development of modular and intuitive robot avatars and preliminary results in the different environments.

II. ROBOT AVATAR DESIGN

Conceptually, for enabling the remotization of a physical operation by means of a robotic avatar, it is necessary to realize a closed loop system as represented in Fig. 2. Three main elements define the overall architecture: a user interface (pilot station), that both collects user control inputs and provides multi-sensory feedback to the pilot. A robot that has mobility, manipulation and perception capabilities sufficient for the required application. Lastly, a reliable communication infrastructure should be granted.

Accordingly, the main requirements for enabling industrial deployment of the JOiiNT LAB avatar are usability, and modularity. Specifically, the development of intuitive interfaces through wearable and immersive devices (i.e. first person experience) is essential for enabling industrial non-roboticist professionals, e.g. technicians or maintenance operators, to become users of the robot avatar. Modular, flexible and reconfigurable hardware and software systems, instead, allows to control through the same framework avatars customized to satisfy the requirements of different applications, both in terms of robot skills and pilot inputs and perception.

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Fig. 2. Conceptual scheme of the JOiiNT LAB teleoperation framework.

III. INDUSTRIAL USE CASES

1) *Welded vessels Inspection*: This use case specifically concerns the inspections of welded joints during the assembly process of large vessels. During the test the pipeline is pressurized and the operator needs to monitor it closely to identify leaks. Remotizing the activity would result in an improved operator safety. Fig. 3(a) shows a photo-sequence of preliminary testing activity on a laboratory mock-up.

2) *Data center maintenance*: This use case regards data center inspection and maintenance. Communication infrastructures have no personnel and often are located in remote places. Whenever a failure occurs, it is critical to address it in the shortest time. Having a robot avatar onsite can prompt the needed action without requiring a technician to reach physically the data center. Fig. 3(b) shows some preliminary testing on a real rack.

3) *Automated production lines maintenance and support*: In the global market, the location of a production line can be installed relatively far from the site where it was manufactured. In such context, a robot avatar enables qualified personnel to assist the client remotely and promptly. Preliminary lab testing was done on the production line scenario shown in Fig. 3(c).

4) *Cranes operations*: Cranes are complex multi-DoF systems which are typically controlled in the joint space. As direct consequence, their operators require years of training to control them in a safe (both for loads and the environment) and efficient way. This specific use case concerns the porting of the avatar technology on cranes, which are by definition large-scale teleoperated robot, with the aim of improving the overall usability of the system. Fig. 3(d) shows the photo-sequence of a crane remotely teleoperated reaching a specific target location.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we presented the JOiiNT LAB avatar framework and its preliminary evaluation in different industrial application. Preliminary experimental activity demonstrated the feasibility of a number of tasks that were defined based on the use cases provided by the companies.

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Fig. 3. Photo-sequences of the robot avatar being tested in different scenarios. Top to bottom: welded vessels inspection, door opening in a data center, machine tending of a production line, and target acquisition.

REFERENCES

- [1] Thomas B Sheridan. Space teleoperation through time delay: Review and prognosis. *IEEE Transactions on robotics and Automation*, 9(5):592–606, 1993.
- [2] Louis L Whitcomb. Underwater robotics: Out of the research laboratory and into the field. In *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation. Symposia Proceedings*, volume 1, pages 709–716, 2000.
- [3] Jeffrey Abouaf. Trial by fire: teleoperated robot targets chernobyl. *IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications*, 18(4):10–14, 1998.
- [4] Simone Fani, Simone Ciotti, Manuel G Catalano, Giorgio Grioli, Alessandro Tognetti, et al. Simplifying telerobotics: Wearability and teleimpedance improves human-robot interactions in teleoperation. *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, 25(1):77–88, 2018.
- [5] Francesca Negrello, Alessandro Settimi, Danilo Caporale, Gianluca Lentini, Mattia Poggiani, Dimitrios Kanoulas, Luca Muratore, et al. Humanoids at work: The walk-man robot in a postearthquake scenario. *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, 25(3):8–22, 2018.
- [6] Maria Rosanna Fossati, Manuel Giuseppe Catalano, Marina Carbone, Gianluca Lentini, et al. Lhf connect: a diy telepresence robot against covid-19. *Strategic Design Research Journal*, 13(3):418–431, 2020.
- [7] Lingyun Chen et al. Drawing elon musk: A robot avatar for remote manipulation. In *2021 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, pages 4244–4251. IEEE, 2021.
- [8] Susumu Tachi. Telexistence. In *Virtual Realities*, pages 229–259. Springer, 2015.